

The Unjournal

Evaluation Summary and Metrics: "Irrigation Strengthens Climate Resilience: Long-term Evidence from Mali using Satellites and Surveys"

Evaluator 1 Evaluator 2 David Reinstein¹ Ben Balmford²

¹The Unjournal, ²University of Exeter

Published on: Oct 08, 2025

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.21428/d28e8e57.8e1125d8>

License: [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License \(CC-BY 4.0\)](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/)

ABSTRACT¹

This paper [1] investigates the impacts of relatively low-cost, small-scale, river-based irrigation in Mali, finding broadly positive and sustained effects on agricultural productivity and nutrition, and reduced conflict in the closest communities. On the other hand, they find *negative* spillovers on surrounding areas. Unjournal evaluators gave mixed ratings, with E1 giving an overall assessment of 75/100 and E2 giving 46/100 (percentiles relative to comparable research). Both appreciated the novel combination of spatial and survey data. Both expressed at least some confidence in the basic results: increased agricultural output (E1 strongly believed this claim), and improved nutritional status of children in the same area (E2 considered this “credible”). E2 expressed substantial doubts regarding the causal interpretation, seeking more “context-specific information on the causal pathway” and investigation of *mechanisms* to inform future “investment and program design.” They also raised specific concerns with the data and measurement, e.g., arguing that “the surveys tend to use recall on household caloric intake rather than important nutrition indicator[s]”. E1 made concrete suggestions for improvements and robustness checks, recommending an updated TWFE methodology and more careful quantification of the output effect “in an area with a larger buffer around the irrigation system”. We, the evaluation managers, raise further identification concerns, including the potential for migration/residential sorting to bias the estimated impact on human outcomes, the potential endogeneity in the timing of irrigation programs (e.g., selection based on decreasing conflict risk), and the need to verify pre-trends are tightly bounded around zero, rather than merely statistical insignificant (see “[issues meriting further evaluation](#)” below). Nonetheless, we believe that these findings are relevant to policy, highlighting the potential of small-scale irrigation to contribute to climate change adaptation, subject to important caveats about spillovers, identification, and the need for more evidence on whether irrigated areas show greater resilience to weather shocks. To read these evaluations, please see the links below.

Evaluations

1. [Evaluation 1](#)
2. [Evaluation 2](#)

Overall ratings

We asked evaluators to provide overall assessments as well as ratings for a range of specific criteria.

I. Overall assessment (See footnote²)

II. Journal rank tier, normative rating (0-5): On a ‘scale of journals’, what ‘quality of journal’ should this be published in?³ Note: 0= lowest/none, 5= highest/best.

	Overall assessment (0-100)	Journal rank tier, normative rating (0-5)
Evaluator 1	75	3.6
Evaluator 2	46	2.5

See “[Metrics](#)” below for a more detailed breakdown of the evaluators’ ratings across several categories. To see these ratings in the context of all Unjournal ratings, with some analysis, see our [data presentation here](#).⁴

See [here](#) for the current full evaluator guidelines, including further explanation of the requested ratings.

Evaluation summaries

Anonymous evaluator 1

This was a very interesting paper with evident care taken to use novel data sources for careful analysis of irrigation and climate resilience. This paper uses detailed data on the exact boundaries of irrigated sites in Northern Mali combined with remotely-sensed data on farm production, water availability, vegetation condition, precipitation, and temperature to estimate the impact of these small-scale, river-based, irrigation investments on agricultural output. A particularly novel aspect of this paper is that it estimates the relationship between irrigation and agricultural outcomes in a conflict zone, where traditional data gathering is likely to be a challenge. The authors use Two Way Fixed Effects to estimate these results, following recent work on heterogeneous treatment effects in TWFE.

The authors demonstrate that Normalized Deviation Water Index (NDWI), which is interpreted as water available to crops, significantly increases after irrigation is introduced, with no evidence of a significant pre-trend. Similarly, the authors find a large increase in Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (a measure of plant green-ness or vegetation health) during the rainy seasons after irrigation was introduced. This is consistent with results of qualitative work suggesting rice yields increased significantly. This is also complemented by increased nutrition from DHS for children living near the irrigation projects. There are some negative effects on child nutrition and agricultural employment more than 4km away from the project. Irrigation also appears to be related to conflict, with sites experiencing significantly [fewer] conflict events immediately at the perimeter, with a slight increase in conflict further away.

Anonymous evaluator 2

One of the article’s strengths is offering a longer time horizon of analysis of smallholder irrigation, which gives insights beyond localized case studies or pilot plots. Another value is that the authors connect spatial data across water, agriculture and nutrition, to provide insight beyond water efficiency or yield gains. The analysis

on longer-term livelihood outcomes may be beneficial for potential decision-making on irrigation policy. However, the article has shortcomings in terms of causal factors and control areas for comparison. For example, [are] the differences in nutritional outcomes related to improved income, increased household consumption of own produce, changes in dietary behavior, market development, or other factors? Context-specific information on the causal pathways are critical for investment and program design.

Metrics

Ratings

[See here](#) for details on the categories below, and the guidance given to evaluators.

	Evaluator 1 Anonymous			Evaluator 2 Anonymous	
Rating category	Rating (0-100)	90% CI (0-100)*	Comments	Rating (0-100)	Comments
Overall assessment ⁵	75	(69, 85)	6	46	
Claims, strength, characterization of evidence ⁷	70	(60, 75)	8	35	
Advancing knowledge and practice ⁹	80	(70, 90)	10	32	11
Methods: Justification, reasonableness, validity, robustness ¹²	75	(70, 85)	13	34	
Logic & communication ¹⁴	75	(70, 80)		40	
Open, collaborative, replicable ¹⁵	80	(70, 90)	16	70	

Real-world relevance 17,18	75	(65, 85)		30	
Relevance to global priorities 19,20	75	(65, 85)		30	

Journal ranking tiers

[See here](#) for more details on these tiers.

	Evaluator 1		Evaluator 2
	Anonymous		Anonymous
Judgment	Ranking tier (0-5)	90% CI	Ranking tier (0-5)
On a 'scale of journals', what 'quality of journal' <i>should</i> this be published in?	3.6	(3.2, 4.2)	2.5
What 'quality journal' do you expect this work <i>will</i> be published in?	3.5	(2.9, 4.0)	3.2
See here for more details on these tiers.	<p><i>We summarize these as:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 0.0: Marginally respectable/Little to no value • 1.0: OK/Somewhat valuable • 2.0: Marginal B-journal/Decent field journal • 3.0: Top B-journal/Strong field journal • 4.0: Marginal A-Journal/Top field journal • 5.0: A-journal/Top journal 		

Claim identification and assessment (summary)

For the full discussions, see the corresponding sections in each linked evaluation.

	Main research claim 21	Belief in claim 22	Suggested robustness checks 23	Important 'implication', policy, credibility 24
--	---	---	---	--

<p>Evaluator 1 Anonymous</p>	<p>The authors argue that small-scale, river-based, irrigation investments in Northern Mali significantly increase agricultural output.</p>	<p>I strongly believe that irrigation did increase agricultural output, for those areas where irrigation was placed.</p>	<p>What would make this claim stronger is a robustness check to understand how much of this agricultural output is being moved from surrounding areas into the new irrigation scheme to understand the effects on the treated area overall.</p>	<p>The implication here is that investments in small-scale irrigation would increase agricultural output even in conflict-prone areas.</p>
<p>Evaluator 2 Anonymous</p>	<p>There is a correlation between an irrigation investment using pumped water in an area of Mali and improved nutritional status of children in the same area.</p>	<p>The basic proposition is credible, but the assumptions about causal relationship are less convincing.</p>	<p>The work would have benefited from a comparative or control, and from much more in-depth social science through a targeted nutritional survey (that considers other indicators of nutrition beyond caloric intake), in depth interviews, and project tracing to understand other investments and contextual factors that may contribute to causation.</p>	<p>The implication here is that investments in small-scale irrigation would increase agricultural output even in conflict-prone areas.</p>

Evaluation managers' discussion

Issues meriting further evaluation

Note, 18 Sep 2025: The points in this subsection come from the evaluation managers, Ben Balmford and David Reinstein. We have not shared these with the authors before posting, but we will do so now.

As evaluation managers, we wanted to highlight some issues in the paper that the evaluators did not discuss in detail.

Evaluator 2's interpretation of "causality" seems closer to what economists would call an exploration of mechanisms, rather than causality in the strict sense of identifying an unbiased estimate of the treatment effect

of an intervention. From an economics perspective, the assumptions underlying the DiD strategy are not directly challenged in their review. Instead, their suggestions are more about clarifying mechanisms by which irrigation has its impacts in this context. Their evaluation highlights the importance of understanding mechanisms for assessing the generalisability and policy relevance of the findings; and ensuring that the measured outcomes are policy relevant. In “econ-speak,” their concerns reinforce the point that identifying mechanisms is crucial not for establishing causality per se, but for understanding how and where impacts might translate across settings.

On causal interpretation, however, we as evaluation managers are somewhat concerned that the irrigation projects could plausibly have been established in particular places and times - for instance, possibly contemporaneous with reductions in (very) local conflict risk or alongside other interventions. If the timing of sites is endogenous, then the credibility of DiD identification is threatened - a point that is not squarely confronted in the paper or in the evaluations. The authors do note that “we confirm that using this quasi-experimental approach, the timing of irrigation at a given site is not correlated with its preceding changes in weather conditions, agricultural outcomes, or community health.” This is reassuring in ruling out some obvious threats, but it does not fully address the possibility that site timing or location is influenced by unobserved factors that also affect later outcomes, or that contemporaneous policy changes overlap with irrigation. The use of district-by-year and region-by-year FEs in specific specifications do help alleviate these concerns, as does the evidence that there are no concurrent, nearby, infrastructure projects. Nonetheless, future work could gather could detail in more depth the precise process for assignment and timing of treatment, using either administrative or anecdotal evidence to reassure that timing is as good as random.

Migration is another reason the measured difference in human outcomes may not reflect the actual impact of irrigation. The authors acknowledge this, raising the possibility of “shifts in labor and other resources toward the newly irrigated sites”, backed up by focus group discussions. But they still report these changes in ways that loosely suggest these are real effects in the abstract and conclusion:

- “Children in nearby communities are less likely to be stunted or wasted due to the irrigation, and conflict risks decrease in the closest communities.”
- “our estimates on nutritional benefits from small-scale irrigation comport with previous finding”

If this migration (i.e., relocation) is substantial, it doesn’t only hold the potential to have “negative impacts on child nutrition and agricultural employment in outlying areas” (and similarly for conflict outcomes). It could also be driving the *positive* observed changes on the treated areas – obviously if healthier people are moving in, the measured average human outcomes will show an increase. They take some mitigation steps and do some robustness checks, but the concern remains. (E.g., for children, they find that effects are strongest for those born *after* project completion, but this still doesn’t rule out selective in-migration of pregnant women/young families).

Their robustness checks and diagnostics are not as solid as we would like. We want to see evidence that the concerning factors are ‘*likely* to be so small as to be inconsequential’. For community health pre-trends they present graphs with pre-period coefficients centered near zero and 95% confidence intervals that cover zero. But the graphs don’t make it clear whether these pre-trends are *tightly bounded around zero*.

Furthermore, some results seem to be missing or hidden. They state “we do not observe differential changes in other household characteristics coinciding with the irrigation introduction in these outlying areas, indicating that the worse stunting and wasting rates are not likely due to shifts in population compositions.” But we could not find any evidence presented about these differences in the article or supplementary materials.

Process notes and resources

Why we chose this paper

This paper was suggested to us by www.aiddata.org/ (by one of the authors) as being among their highest-value work meriting further evaluation. (See our ‘evaluating research from impact-oriented organizations’ initiative discussed [here](#))

Evaluation process

We shared the [linked “bespoke evaluation notes”](#) with the evaluators, providing them with context and further suggestions for evaluation work.

Author engagement

As noted, this paper was suggested to us by one of the authors when we reached out to <https://www.aiddata.org/>.

They have been very responsive and offered suggestions. They decided to submit a brief response:

We appreciate the reviewers and evaluation managers' comments. While we strove to sufficiently isolate the plausibly exogenous spatiotemporal variation in the irrigation intervention to allow for reliable causal identification, we understand that some readers may still have concerns. We agree with the evaluation managers' suggestion that future work could gather more details on the precise process of treatment assignment (recognizing that we did spend considerable effort toward this already). We also concur with the reviewers comments that further exploring all of the mechanisms behind our diverse results could also help readers in generalizing findings to other contexts.

As always if they wish to provide a longer response in the future, we will share it here.

Other (AI powered) resources

We're sharing some LLM/AI resources. *Readers:* Please let us know if you find these useful. We're doing this on a trial basis. *Of course we can not vouch for the accuracy of any LLM/AI responses.* [7 Nov 2025 — the ChatGPT links are no longer publicly accessible; we're working to fix this, let us know if you are interested.]

1. [This "notebookLM"](#) of these evaluations, our discussion, and the original paper. Please let us know if you find this useful.
2. A series of GPT-5 and GPT Deep Research mock evaluations. We shared the paper (and the supplement, where noted below), and asked it to follow our [evaluation guidelines](#), as well (where indicated below) as to ignore author names/institutions, and to consider our bespoke notes.

7 Nov 2025 — the ChatGPT links are no longer publicly accessible; we're working to fix this, please let us know if you are interested. ²⁵

References

[1] Ariel BenYishay, Rachel Sayers, Kunwar Singh, Seth Goodman, Madeleine Walker, Souleymane Traore, Mascha Rauschenbach, Martin Noltze, Irrigation strengthens climate resilience: Long-term evidence from Mali using satellites and surveys, *PNAS Nexus*, Volume 3, Issue 2, February 2024, pgae022, <https://doi.org/10.1093/pnasnexus/pgae022>

Footnotes

1. This abstract was written jointly by David Reinstein and Ben Balmford. [↵](#)
2. We asked them to rank this paper "heuristically" as a percentile "relative to all serious research in the same area that you have encountered in the last three years." We requested they "consider all aspects of quality, credibility, importance to knowledge production, and importance to practice." [↵](#)
3. See ranking tiers discussed [here](#). [↵](#)
4. Note: if you are reading this before, or soon after this has been publicly released, the ratings from this paper may not yet have been incorporated into that data presentation. [↵](#)
5. Judge the quality of the research heuristically. Consider all aspects of quality, credibility, importance to knowledge production, and importance to practice.

[↵](#)

6.

A LONG COMMENT ... Excellent as an overview, and important for global health, but unfortunately somewhat disappointing about ways to address global catastrophic risks

[Editor's note: the evaluator has explained that they have not based their assessment on this point; we do not intend 'Relevance to Global Priorities' to factor into the overall assessment) [↵](#)

7. "Do the authors do a good job of (i) stating their main questions and claims, (ii) providing strong evidence and powerful approaches to inform these, and (iii) correctly characterizing the nature of their evidence?"

This was on the newer form only [↵](#)

8. For the "Claims" rating, I think the results could be closer to the claim that this paper addresses climate "resilience". The claim that these results represent resilience would be stronger if linked to climate shocks rather than overall agricultural productivity. [↵](#)

9.

To what extent does the project contribute to the field or to practice, particularly in ways that are directly or indirectly relevant to global priorities and impactful interventions?

[↵](#)

10. This paper provides new and interesting knowledge, and the application of remote sensing to generate data during a period of conflict is a clear advance where other traditional field data methods would not have been feasible. This is a notable advance to knowledge with clear practical implications. [↵](#)

11. Noting that knowledge and practice should have separate ratings. This may contribute to the academic literature, but there are risks to practice from using the content without further nuance and critique. [↵](#)

12. Are methods clearly justified and explained? Are methods and their underlying assumptions reasonable? Are the results likely to be robust to changes in the assumptions? Have the authors avoided bias and questionable research practices? [↵](#)

13. The methods used here are reasonable and appropriate, though the literature on Two Way Fixed Effects is rapidly changing and other more recently-introduced methods might also be considered here. [↵](#)

14. Are concepts clearly defined? Is the reasoning transparent? Are conclusions consistent with the evidence (or formal proofs) presented? Are the data and/or analysis, including tables and figures, relevant to the argument? [↵](#)

15.

Would another researcher be able to replicate the analysis? Are the method and its details explained sufficiently? Is the source of the data clear? Is the data made as widely available as possible, with clear labeling and explanation? Do the authors provide resources that are likely to enable future research and meta-analysis?

[↵](#)

16. Methods are clearly explained and links to data sources are precise. [↵](#)

17.

Does the paper consider real-world relevance and deal with policy and implementation questions? Are the setup, assumptions, and focus realistic and relevant to practitioners?

[↵](#)

18.

The latter ratings were merged in the newer form

"Are the paper's chosen topic and approach likely to be useful to global priorities, cause prioritization, and high-impact interventions?"

"Does the paper consider real-world relevance and deal with policy and implementation questions? Are the setup, assumptions, and focus realistic? Do the authors report results that are relevant to practitioners? Do they provide useful quantified estimates (costs, benefits, etc.)?" [↵](#)

19. Are the paper's chosen topic and approach likely to be useful to global priorities, cause prioritization, and high-impact interventions? [↵](#)

20.

The latter ratings were merged in the newer form

"Are the paper's chosen topic and approach likely to be useful to global priorities, cause prioritization, and high-impact interventions?"

"Does the paper consider real-world relevance and deal with policy and implementation questions? Are the setup, assumptions, and focus realistic? Do the authors report results that are relevant to practitioners? Do they provide useful quantified estimates (costs, benefits, etc.)?" [↵](#)

21.

The evaluator was given the following instructions:

Identify the most important and impactful factual claim this research makes – e.g., a binary claim or a point estimate or prediction.

Please state the authors' claim precisely and quantitatively. Identify the source of the claim (i.e., cite the paper), and briefly mention the evidence underlying this. We encourage you to explain why you believe this claim is important, either here, or in the text of your report. [↵](#)

22. Evaluators were asked: To what extent do you **believe** the claim you stated above? Feel free to express this either a. in terms of the probability of the claim being true, b. as a credible interval for the parameter being estimated, or c. however you feel comfortable. [↵](#)

23.

We asked:

[Optional] What additional information, evidence, replication, or robustness check would make you substantially more (or less) confident in this claim?

Feel free to refer to the main body of your evaluation here; you don't need to repeat yourself. Please specify how you would perform this robustness check (etc.) as precisely as you are willing. E.g., if you suggest a particular estimation command in a statistical package, this could be very helpful for future robustness replication work. [↵](#)

24.

We asked:

[Optional] Identify the important **implication** of the above claim for funding and policy choices? To what extent do you **believe** this implication? How should it inform policy choices?

Note: this 'implication' could be suggested by the evaluation manager in some cases. As an example of an 'implication' ... in a global health context, the 'main claim' might suggest that a vitamin supplement intervention, if scaled up, would save lives at a \$XXXXX per life saved.

We did not ask this in the 'applied stream' as it is most likely redundant.

[↵](#)

25. [↵](#)

References

1. Ariel BenYishay, Rachel Sayers, Kunwar Singh, Seth Goodman, Madeleine Walker, Souleymane Traore, Mascha Rauschenbach, Martin Noltze, Irrigation strengthens climate resilience: Long-term evidence from Mali using satellites and surveys, *PNAS Nexus*, Volume 3, Issue 2, February 2024, pgae022, <https://doi.org/10.1093/pnasnexus/pgae022> ↵